

FROM VICTORIAN SOCIETY TO LITERARY REALISM: THE EVOLUTION OF CRITICAL REALISM IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Abstract

Victorian literature is defined by the period of time in which it was written, not a central philosophy or style. However, a lot of Victorian literature does have particular themes or showcases similar forms and styles. This was caused by changing trends in thinking and taste. Following the Romantic period, writers of the Victorian age turned away from the abstract expressionism of the former period and focused on realism, with an attention towards social issues and the sciences.

Both poetry and fictional prose were popular throughout the Victorian Age, producing some of the greatest writers in English. And during this time, the novel became the leading literary genre in English. A lot of prominent writers became aware of the social injustices around them and tried to depict them in their works. Thus this period was mirrored in literature by the appearance of a new trend, the Critical Realism.

Victorian writers used the novel as a means to protest against the evils in contemporary social and economic life and to picture the world in a realistic way. Their greatness also lies in their profound humanism. Their sympathy lies with the ordinary people. They believed in the good qualities of the human heart.

The novel's ubiquity today can be traced back to its popularity in Victorian England; the greatest Victorian novelists are remembered for their overall artistry and their social observations and critiques.

Keywords: Victorian literature, social injustice, critical realism, democratic viewpoint.

The history of English literature may well be thought too large a venture for one volume, let alone one historian. Literary contents have obviously changed over the centuries. It is less obvious how far the means of representing life have gradually changed through the history of literary forms. Sometimes these have social or economic causes, but more often they are developments to literature- shifts of fashion, deeper movements.

English Literature has had a long and trying way of evolution, reflecting the history of the country and nation. It has undergone effects of historical periods that raced the literature to its pick. Amidst them was "The Victorian Era" (1832-1901), a period of Queen Victoria's reign.

Queen Victoria had the longest reign in British history, and the cultural, political, economic, industrial and scientific changes that occurred during her reign were quite remarkable.

The Victorian age, the great period of rapid changes and contradictions is subdivided into three phases:

1. Early Victorian (1832- 48)
2. Mid- Victorian (1848- 70)
3. Late- Victorian (1870- 1901)

The early Period (1832- 1848) - A Time of Troubles

The early phase has been characterized as the Time of Troubles. In 1832 the passing of a Reform Bill had seemed to satisfy many of the demands of the middle classes who were gradually taking over control of England's economy. The bill extended the right to vote to all men owning property. In the early 1840's a severe depression with wider spread unemployment conditions in the new industrial and coal- mining areas were sufficiently inflammatory to create revolution. Workers and their families in the slums of such cities as Man-

chester lived like packs of rats in a sewer and the conditions under which women and children toiled in mines and factories were unimaginably brutal. Elizabeth Barrett's poem "The cry of the children" (1843) tells us about children of fire years of age who dragged heavy tubs of coal through low- ceiling mine- passages for sixteen hours a day. Although the owners of mines and factories are blamed for such conditions these owners regarded themselves as innocent. There was an immense and continually increasing population, no adequate demand for labor, no confidence, but a universal alarm. The country was drawn in a deep sea of sorrows that seemed to be away of any possible way outs. To crown it all, nobody pretended to be able to point out any remedy.

This Time of Troubles left its mark on some early Victorian literature. In his novel "Sybil" (1854) Benjamin Disraeli chose an appropriate subtitle, "The two nations"- a phrase that pointed up the line dividing the England nation into the rich and the poor. The author showed off the real life of England, its social strata - the life the poor led in brutality, rudeness and how confidently the rich dwelled without tasting the poor life

Mid-Victorian Period (1848- 1870). Economic Prosperity and Controversy.

This second phase of the Victorian Age had many harassing problems, but it was a time of prosperity. Great development was noticed in science as well. Darwin's great treatise, "The Origin of Species" (1859) brought new views on humanity. Most readers recognized that Darwin's theory of natural selection conflicted with the concept of creation derived from the Quran, Bible, and other sacred books; thus they didn't accept his theory at all.

The Late Period (1870- 1901). Decay of Victorian Value.

This final phase of the century was a time of serenity and security, the age of house parties and long

weekends in the country. Life in London was for many an exhilarating heyday. In 1867, Under Prime Minister Disraeli's guidance, a second reform Bill had been passed which extended the right to vote to sections of the working classes and this made labor a political force.

In poetry, prose fiction essays, history, philosophy and scientific treatises, the Victorian age has done good work. The most eminent writers of the period are Browning and Tennyson in poetry Thackeray, Dickens and George Elliot in prose fiction; Carlyle, Ruskin and Mathew Arnold in essay writing; Herbert Spencer, Cardinal Newman and Sir William Hamilton in various types of philosophy; Tyndell and Huxley in science. Prose takes higher rank in the Victorian than in the preceding age. [1, 93]

In Victorian period appeared a new literary trend—Critical Realism. English critical realism of the 19th century flourished in the 1840s and early. It found its expression mainly in the writing of novels. The critical realists, most of whom were novelists, described with much vividness and artistic skill the chief traits of the English society and criticised the capitalist system from a democratic viewpoint. [1, 52] Eminent representatives of Critical Realism were writer- realists Dickens, Thackeray, Thomas Hardy, Bronte, Cornel, Samuel Battler, Bernard Show, poet-chartists Johns and Linton.

The writers of this period putting social ideas in the focus of views led the reader to the idea of inhumanity and injustice society. Dickens and Thackeray since the early years of their creativity had defended the honest social Proceeding with the best traditions of realistic literature they were approving democratic principles of art. Putting Social ideas in the focus of views, those writers - realists led the reader to the idea of inhumanity and injustice society. English realists addressed significant problem of their epoch - the conflict of proletariat and bourgeoisie; since Dickens in his "Hard Times", Bronte in "Sherley", Gasckel in "Mary Barton" strictly depicted the problem of interrelation, conflicts and controversies between capitalists and workers. As a result, creation of the English writer - realists has a bright tendency of anti - bourgeoisie. Marks were writing: "The bright group of cotemporary English writers whose expressive and significant notes exposed. The world with its political and social reality rather than professional politics, publicists or moralists did. It was the writers who revealed all stratum of bourgeoisie, starting from "respected" tenants and valuable paper holders, and finishing with small shopkeepers and clerks in advocate offices. There is a question: "How did Dickens and Thackeray, Mrs. Bronte and Mrs. Gasckel depict those respected men of respected society?" [5] They depicted them as vividly as they are - self confident, pompous, ignorant and low leveled tyrants. Characteristic peculiarity of English realists is a craft of satirical exposure. Satire, for its diversity and richness - is the sharpest implement of Dickens and Thackeray. [6] By criticizing rotten society with its all deficiencies and contradictions, they also revealed moral innocence, diligence, disinterestedness and firmness of simple people. In depiction of people one can

see a deep sense of humanism in English writers' work, especially in Dickens. His positive ideals, Dickens could see in disinterest and honest toilers. According to Dickens, those poor, simple people are the sole real happy ones despite the all injustice and cruelty of society. However, English critical realists were far away of the conception of historical valuation regularity. They had no direct relation to "worker Movements" surrounding the country.

Depicting people's strive to a better life writers were also revealing the ways for solutions of these problems. In the second part of XIX century struggle of the classes didn't cease yet; worker movements were still observed. In 50-60s at the same time with Dickens there known other literary men like Thackeray, Emily Bronte, Elizabeth Gaskell and George Elliot. Philosophy of Positivism has brightly displayed the characteristic creation of them. Main characters of their books are common people with their hard and trying life. Bourgeois men of letters devoted to the interests of own class, not only by amusing and flattering since a great number of them frankly praised and supported military aggression and colonial invasions of British Empire. Alfred Tennyson who never exposed knighthood of Middle Ages now was glorifying prospering Victorian England. Though in such a hard opportunity best custom and principles of the art of critical realism were developing in the creation of outstanding writer- Ch. Dickens. [7]

Ch. Dickens was the greatest critical realist in XIX century English literature. K. Marx in an article published in The New York Tribune in 1854 gave the following characterization of the English critical realists. The present brilliant school of novelists in England, whose descriptions have revealed more political and social truth to the world than have all the politicians, publicists and moralists added together, has pictured all sections of the middle class, beginning with the "respectable" owner of government stocks, and finishing with the small shopkeeper. [3, 124] How have they been described by Dickens, Thackeray, Charlotte Bronte and Mrs. Gaskell, as full of self conceit, petty tyranny and ignorance? And the civilized world confirmed their verdict in a damning epigram which it has pinned on that class, that it was servile to its social superiors and despotic to its social inferiors, Of the writers named by Marx, Dickens, and Thackeray were the most outstanding. Creativity of Charles Dickens opens a new bright page in the history of Critical Realism of England. The whole epoch of Evolution of the English literature is concerned with his name. Dickens belongs to that group of great writers that has been pride of the national English Culture .

With striking force and truthfulness, he pictured bourgeois civilization, showing the misery and sufferings of the common people. In his novels, Dickens pulls out the masks of English Bourgeoisie. [4, 559] He directs his stroke against infinite hypocrisy and egoism. By depicting main characters of his novels, (Oliver Twist, Nicholas Nickleby) the author reveals painful life of thousands of unfortunate people. In Oliver Twist Dickens tells the story of an orphan boy of unknown parentage. Born in a workhouse, brought up under cruel

conditions, the hero runs away from the workhouse to London where he falls into the hands of a gang of thieves. He is rescued from them by the benevolent rich Mr. Brownlow, but thieves make him join them once again and partake in their foul dealings.[8] The novel ends with Oliver's adoption by Mr. Brownlow. The adventures of the boy-hero were used by Dickens to describe the lower depths of London. He makes his reader aware of the inhumanity of city life under the conditions of capitalism. Dickens describes here the awful conditions under which the children of the poor were brought up, and exposes the cruelty of the bourgeois philanthropists.[2, 480]

Another critical realist, William Makepeace Thackeray, was a severe critic of the English society. Thackeray's novels are mainly a satirical portrayal of the upper stratum of society. The writer made his way to popularity much more slowly than Dickens. These two men, who became friends and generous rivals, were very different in character and disposition. Among his novels "Vanity Fair" (1847-48) is Thackeray's masterpiece. For the lifelikeness of its characters, it is one of the most remarkable creations in fiction. In "Vanity Fair" certain classes of society satirized. Their intrigues, frivolities and caprices, flippant characters are dealt with. Thackeray probes almost every weakness, vanity and ambition which leads humanity to strive for a place in society. In "Henry Esmond" (1852) Thackeray gives an enduring picture of high life in the 18th century. "The History of Pendennis" (1849) and "The Virginians" (1857-1859) are both popular novels. "The English Humorists of the 18th century" (1853) and "The Four Georges" (1860) are among his essays. Thackeray is an uncompromising realist and satirist. He doesn't label his characters with external marks, but enters into communion with their souls. His method of lying bares their motives and an action is strictly modern.

The other representative of the Great Victorian Period was Mary Ann Evans, known to her family as Marian and to her reader as George Eliot (1857-1876). George Eliot does not regard the novel as a vehicle for entertainment alone, but rather as a means of revealing the human condition. Like George Meredith, "she is the embodiment of philosophy in fiction," as Oscar Wilde remarked in 1897. Examining her central characters in depth, Eliot often abandons conventional plot-formulae by failing to provide an entirely happy ending. Her stories usually end somberly, without a real hero or heroine emerging. Eliot began her greatest work, *Middlemarch*, in 1867 and completed it in 1872; it was published in *Blackwood's Magazine* in eight monthly installments, although she had finished only three when the serial run began in 1871. She envisioned the *Vincey* part of the story as complete in itself in 1869; the story's realism she carefully investigated provincial hospitals, medical practices, and physicians, rather than accept conventional thinking and stereotypes. Although she was to write one final lengthy novel (*Daniel Deronda*) before her death in 1880, it is for *Middlemarch* that she is still remembered as "The Victorian Sage," a remarkable achievement for a woman in nineteenth-century Britain. *Adam Bede* (1859) was her first full-length

novel. It was an immediate success, but attracted fervent public gossip as to who the real author was. When it was discovered that Eliot was Mrs. Marian Evans Lewes, many castigated her but she was also lauded by friends, fellow authors, and feminists. *The Lifted Veil* (1859) reflects the personal struggles Eliot went through as a woman and author in the spotlight since the success of *Adam Bede*. She still felt self-doubt at times and had bouts of depression--this sensitive inner-life reflected in many of the portraits painted of her.

Other novelists who adhere to critical realism were Charlotte Brontë, Emily Brontë, Elizabeth Gaskell, and Thomas Hardy.

The Brontës were the world's most famous literary family. Charlotte, Emily and Anne Brontë were the authors of some of the best-loved books in the English language. Charlotte's novel *Jane Eyre* (1847), Emily's *Wuthering Heights* (1847), and Anne's *The Tenant of Wildfell Hall* (1848) were written in this house over a hundred and fifty years ago, yet their power still moves readers today. To find two writers of genius in one family would be rare, but to find several writers in one household is unique in the history of literature. Charlotte and Emily are ranked among the world's greatest novelists; Anne is a powerful underrated author, and both their father, the Revd. Patrick Brontë, and brother Branwell also saw their own works in print.

Surprisingly, the enduring myth of the Brontës living a life of unrelieved isolation and tragedy was, to some extent, created unintentionally by the Brontës themselves. In choosing to write under pseudonyms, the sisters drew an immediate veil of mystery around them.

Like most authors, the Brontës drew upon their imaginations, on their personal experiences and the landscape and characters around them, but their mature poems and novels are also rooted in the themes of the early writings of their childhood and adolescence. The following works were written by the Brontë Family: "*Jane Eyre*" (1846), "*Villette*" (1853), "*Shirley*" (1849), "*The Professor*" (1857) (Charlotte Brontë); "*Wuthering Heights*" (1847) (Emily Brontë); "*Agnes Grey*" (1847), "*The Tenant of Wildfell Hall*" (1848) (Anne Brontë); "*The Works of Patrick Branwell Brontë*" : An Edition (Vol I).

Elizabeth Gaskell's name is definitely among the realists as well. (1810-1865) Gaskell's first novel, *Mary Barton*, was published anonymously in 1848. The best known of her remaining novels are *Cranford* (1853), *North and South* (1854), and *onful Wives and Daughters* (1865). She became popular for her writing, especially her ghost story writing, aided by her friend Charles Dickens, who published her work in his magazine *Household Words*. Her ghost stories are quite distinct in style from her industrial fiction and belong to the Gothic fiction genre. Even though her writing conforms to Victorian conventions (including signing her "Mrs. Gaskell"), name Gaskell usually frames her stories as critiques of contemporary attitudes, particularly those toward women, with complex narratives and dynamic female characters. [10] In addition to her fiction, Gaskell also wrote the first biography of Charlotte Brontë, which played a significant role in developing her fellow writer's reputation. Gaskell was well-known

for her following novels: "Mary Barton" (1848), "Cranford" (1851- 1853), "Ruth" (1853), "North and South" (1854-1855), "Sylvia's Lovers" (1863), "Cousin Phillis" (1864), "Wives and Daughters: An Everyday Story" (1865). She was the author of short stories like "Libbie Marsh's Three Ears" (1847), "Christmas Storms and Sunshine" (1848), "The Squire's Story" (1853), "Half a Life-time Ago" (1855), "An Accursed Race" (1855), "The Poor Clare (1856)", "The Manchester Marriage" (1858) a chapter of *A House to Let*, co-written with Charles Dickens, Wilkie Collins, and Adelaide Anne Procter, *The Half-brothers* (1859), *The Grey Woman* (1861). [9]As a Unitarian dissenter living in the industrial town of Manchester, Gaskell wrote with compassion but at-times bold frankness about controversial issues of the day including the general poverty of the working classes, the hardships of men working in mines and factories, and women working in mills, After enjoying an idyllic middle childhood in the country, she was shocked and saddened to see families living in slums eking out a miserable existence. Time and again she would cause controversy among her privileged Victorian readership with her characters and themes. While trying to balance her domestic duties with burgeoning literary pursuits, Gaskell inevitably drew upon her own experiences with various charitable organisations in assisting the poor to create her now famous fictitious works.

All in all, today the greatest Victorian novelists are remembered for their overall artistry and their social observations and critiques. The English critical realists of the 19th century not only gave a satirical portrayal of the bourgeoisie and all the ruling classes, but also showed profound sympathy for the common people. In their best works, the greed and hypocrisy of the upper classes are contrasted with the honesty and good-heartedness of the obscure "simple people" of the lower classes. Hence humor and satire abound in the

English realistic novels of the 19th Critical realism reveals the corrupting influence of the rule of cash upon human nature. Here lies the essentially democratic and humanistic character of critical realism.

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